

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness and Purchase Intention of Sliced Tobacco for PT. Taru Martani 1918

Mega Anjani¹, Prawira Fajarindra Belgiawan²

^{1,2} School of Business Management, Insitut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: Tobacco is a leading agricultural commodity in Indonesia. So that it can improve the national economy and improve the welfare of local farmers. Cigarette consumers in Indonesia are very high because people in Indonesia have a smoking culture that has been passed down from generation to generation until today. This triggers the development of cigarette companies in the market. PT Taru Martani is a tobacco company that produces sliced tobacco and cigars. PT Taru Martani has been operating since 1918. However, brand awareness at PT Taru Martani is still low. Therefore, this study aims to obtain a strategy to increase brand awareness and purchase intention at PT Taru Martani. The external analysis used by the author is PESTLE analysis, Porter's Five Forces analysis, customer analysis, and competitor analysis. While the internal analysis uses marketing mix analysis, VRIO analysis, and STP analysis. Then internal and external factors were analyzed using SWOT analysis, TOWS analysis, and QSPM analysis. Based on the results of the research, it is known that the causes of problems at Taru Martani are: lack of brand awareness, the use of digital platforms that are not optimal, and product distribution that is not widely distributed. The strategies generated based on the analysis are marketing strategies based on culture and lifestyle, increasing and expanding promotional activities by utilizing social media platforms and online marketing channels to increase visibility and brand awareness, increase product information updates and communicate the advantages of Taru Martani products to consumers, expand networks distribution, focus on product and service quality, as well as discount and promotional offer strategies.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, External Analysis, Internal Analysis, Tobacco.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, e-cigarettes are very popular in Indonesia. Many conventional cigarette users switch to e-cigarettes for various reasons. The reason that is often heard is because electric cigarettes are cheaper than conventional cigarettes that are widely circulated. This makes conventional cigarette companies rack their brains to compete with the presence of e-cigarettes in society. While on the other hand, the government increased cigarette excise. As is known, the government has just announced an increase in the average excise rate on tobacco products for 2 years at once by 10% in 2023 and 2024. For machine-rolled kretek cigarettes (SKM) class I and II, the average excise rate increase is 11.5% to 11.75%. For class I and II machine white cigarettes (SPM), the excise rate was increased by 11% to 12%. Then for hand-rolled kretek cigarettes (SKT) groups I, II, and III, the excise rate will be increased by 5% [5].

PT Taru Martani is a company engaged in the tobacco industry. The types of products sold by PT Taru Martani are sliced tobacco and cigars. This type of product is a type of conventional cigarettes. PT Taru Martani needs to follow the current business problem situation in order to compete with e-cigarettes as a competitor. Marketing promotion for Taru Martani was minimal, mostly only canvas, social media, and promotional media (jar displays, t-shirts, banners). For example, promotion on social media Instagram is also very minimal compared to other cigarette industries, especially e-cigarettes. This can be seen from the number of followers of Taru Martani, which only has 6182 followers and is not very active in daily posts. So that it can affect brand awareness and lead to low sales. The use of Instagram and the traditional marketing promotion tool Taru Martani is considered less effective due to the decrease in the number of sales transactions.

Based on preliminary interviews conducted with 10 consumers of Taru Martani products who still consume Taru Martani products and no longer consume Taru Martani products, on average they have consumed Taru Martani products for 3 years. They started using Taru Martani products during the pandemic, because during the pandemic many people experienced a decrease in their income. So that Taru Martani sliced tobacco is an alternative to the cigarettes they usually consume, this is because Taru Martani sliced tobacco has a lower price than cigarettes on the market. Taru Martani sliced tobacco includes hand-rolled kretek cigarettes which must be rolled before consumption. Besides the low price, they also like the taste and aroma of Taru Martani products.

Most of them know Taru Martani's products from friends (word of mouth) and from those who have visited Taru Martani Cafe. Taru Martani Cafe sells tobacco products from Taru Martani. The Cafe also offers bundling promos several times if you buy with coffee. Meanwhile, 4 out of 10 consumers who no longer consume Taru Martani products have reasons to stop using Taru Martani products because they rarely smoke, and because they have moved outside the city of Yogyakarta. For those who live outside the city of Yogyakarta, it is difficult to get Taru Martani products.

A preliminary survey was also conducted on 81 active smokers, the majority of whom were in Yogyakarta. The goal is whether many people know Taru Martani's products or not. From the survey results it was found that 39.5% of the public knew about Taru Martani products and 60.5% did not know about Taru Martani products.

Some consumers have stopped consuming Taru Martani products because they no longer smoke, besides that there are also those who have moved from Yogyakarta. The complaint is that those who moved from Yogyakarta no longer use Taru Martani products because Taru Martani products are difficult to find outside the city (not all cities have Taru Martani products). It's different if you are in Yogyakarta, it's easier to find. Even so, usually only people who buy Taru Martani products know about Taru Martani products. For people who don't know about Taru Martani products, most likely they won't try, buy, or even want to know about it. Because they don't know. This study aims to solve this problem in order to increase sales through brand awareness and revive the culture of hand-rolled clove cigarettes.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The following is a conceptual framework that the authors have developed after exploring the problems that arise in the company and based on previous research:

The lack of brand awareness of Taru Martani which seeks to encourage purchase intention is the inspiration for this research. To increase purchase intention by increasing brand awareness, an appropriate marketing plan is needed.

The following table is an explanation of the dimensions based on each variable:

Variable	Dimension
Social Media	1. Context 2. Communication 3. Collaboration 4. Connection
Distribution	1. Marketing channels 2. Marketing scope/Number of outlets 3. Location/Easy to reach 4. Product Inventory/Completeness 5. Transportation
Brand Awareness	1. Easy to remember 2. Famous 3. Remember Brands
Product Attributes	1. Taste

	2. Brand Image/Reputation
	3. Promotion
	4. Tar & Nicotine content
	5. Packaging
	6. Fragrance
	7. Cigarette Density
	8. Ease of Obtaining
	9. Price
Purchase Intention	1. Attention
	2. Interest
	3. Desire
	4. Conviction

Social Media on Brand Awareness

Social media has a big impact on how well-known a company's products are in the neighborhood. It is based on the findings of a study employing a correlation bivariate technique, which showed that social media had a substantial impact on any independent variables with values (Brand awareness of a company's goods in the general public) [13]. Brand recognition is greatly influenced by social media marketing. Social media platforms provide for better exposure and knowledge of information [3].

H1: Social Media positively influences Brand Awareness

Distribution on Brand Awareness

Consumer brand awareness will increase as product distribution becomes more extensive [7]. This backs up Smith's 1992, [6] notion that distribution intensity aids in the growth of brand recognition and awareness. Brand awareness of brand names is positively impacted by distribution intensity [10].

H2: Distribution positively influences Brand Awareness

Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention

According to [1] [11], companies with strong awareness and a positive reputation may encourage customer purchase intention. The more well-known a brand is, the more likely consumers are to trust it and make a purchase. Variable brand awareness research by [14] on purchase intention also reveals a favorable and substantial impact.

H3: Brand Awareness positively influences Purchase Intention

Product Attributes on Purchase Intention

According to a preliminary investigation, product characteristics positively affect purchasing decisions [2]. According to studies by Subagio [12] and Akpoyomare [4], product attributes have a favourable and substantial influence on purchasing decisions. Consumer purchasing decisions can be seen as a process in which consumers evaluate alternative products on the strength of various attributes and on the basis of what marketers differentiate and set their brands apart from the competition.

H4: Product Attribute positively influences Purchase Intention

METHODOLOGY

The resources used in analyzing are primary data and secondary data. Secondary data was in the form of interviews with Taru Martani's marketing department and Taru Martani consumers, distribution of questionnaires to 200 respondents and observations. The data analysis method used a sample of 30 respondents and then tested the validity and reliability tests before distributing the questionnaires to 200 respondents. Secondary data comes from internal company data, websites, and previous research. The study was conducted at PT Taru Martani between January 2023 and June 2023. A descriptive methodology was used. This approach makes it possible to identify internal and external strategic elements, alternative strategies, and priorities.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

To find out the problems that occur at PT Taru Martani and provide solutions to these problems, the author must analyze the company's environment. Analysis conducted by the author in the form of external analysis and internal analysis. External analysis uses PESTLE analysis, Porter's 5 Forces analysis, customer analysis, and competitor analysis. Meanwhile, internal analysis uses marketing mix analysis, VRIO analysis, and STP analysis. Then internal and external factors were analyzed using SWOT analysis, TOWS analysis, and QSPM analysis.

A. PESTLE Analysis

PESTLE analysis is used to determine political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental factors whether these factors are threats or opportunities for Taru Martani. The political factor at PT Taru Martani poses a threat to the company because the Indonesian government has issued a law on tobacco control, imposed high taxes on tobacco products to reduce tobacco consumption and increase state revenues. The economic factor is an opportunity for PT Taru Martani because the low economic situation will make people who consume cigarettes switch to cheap cigarettes, including PT Taru Martani's products. Social factors become opportunities because the culture, habits and views of the Indonesian people towards tobacco can influence the demand for, sales and profits of tobacco companies. In addition, social influence can increase the demand for cigarettes. The technological factor is a threat because technological advances have led to the development of e-cigarettes and other alternative tobacco products, which can have an impact on consumption of traditional tobacco including Taru Martani. The legal factor is a threat because the Indonesian government has implemented various laws and regulations related to the tobacco industry, such as the Tobacco Control Law and the National Tobacco Control Strategy, Minister of Finance Regulation 161/PMK.04/2022 explaining that tobacco products are subject to import duties, and Legal actions related to smoking-related illness or death can result in lawsuits and financial losses for tobacco companies. Environmental factors are a threat to companies because the environment can also affect the tobacco industry due to crop failure, this will affect the supply of raw materials for making tobacco.

B. Porter's 5 Forces Analysis

Porter's 5 Forces analysis is used to analyze:

Competition in the tobacco industry is high because it is a very competitive industry. In this industry there are many brands competing for a bigger market share. Competition in the sliced tobacco industry can be seen from several aspects, including product quality, price, marketing, and innovation. The large number of Indonesian people who consume cigarettes, so each brand tries to maintain its market share and develop its business in a more innovative and effective way; The potential for new entrants to the industry is low because it is difficult for new companies to establish conventional cigarette companies because they have to educate culture, history, and have distinctive characteristics regarding the taste and aroma of the product; Bargaining Power of Suppliers is low because many companies enter into contracts with suppliers, besides that PT Taru Martani has more than one supplier and does not depend on one supplier; Bargaining Power of Buyers is high because customer power greatly influences the price of Taru Martani products. Customers can influence the price and quality of services provided. There are alternative products or brands that are generally offered by the market, but prices with good service and ease of obtaining products as well as offering certain special characteristics will be chosen by customers; The threat of substitute products is high because there are new types of cigarettes that are already on the market, for example e-cigarettes.

C. Customer Analysis

Customer analysis using SEM PLS. Convergent validity is used to measure the extent of the relationship between constructs and latent variables. If the correlation value is more than 0.7 then it meets convergent validity. Based on the results obtained by the author, all loading factors have a value of > 0.7. So it can be concluded that latent variable indicators already have good convergent values. R square result of Brand Awareness is 0.231, it means social media and distribution variables, is only able to explain 23.1% of this phenomenon. While the remaining 76.9% there are other variables that are not explained that affect brand awareness.

R square result of Purchase Intention is 0.271, is brand awareness and product attribute variables, is only able to explain 27.1% of this phenomenon. While the remaining 72.9% have unexplained variables that affect purchase intention.

Variable	P Value
Social Media → Purchase Intention	0.000
Distribution → Brand Awareness	0.000
Brand Awareness → Purchase Intention	0.000
Product Attributes → Brand Awareness	0.018

Based on the results obtained, it appears that all variables have a significant relationship (positive value). That means H1, H2, H3, and H4 are accepted.

Hypothesis	P Value	Conclusion
H1 : Social Media positively influences Brand Awareness	Accepted	Social Media positively influences Brand Awareness
H2 : Distribution positively influences Brand Awareness	Accepted	Social Media positively influences Brand Awareness
H3 : Brand Awareness positively influences Purchase Intention	Accepted	Brand Awareness positively influences Purchase Intention
H4 : Product Attribute positively influences Purchase Intention	Accepted	Product Attribute positively influences Purchase Intention

D. Competitor Analysis

Competitors are determined based on companies that produce sliced tobacco with almost the same market and in the area of Java Island. Understanding competitor analysis allows one to recognize the strength and weakness of businesses in an industry. This can be useful in figuring out how to sell and distribute things.

	PT Taru Martani	Queen Bee	PT Indonesian Tobacco Tbk	Strength/Weakness for Taru Martani
Product variation	Has 5 product variations on sliced tobacco. Offers products weighing 30-75 grams for sliced tobacco.	Has 2 product variations. Offers products weighing 60 grams and 1000 grams for sliced tobacco.	Has 3 product variations. Offers products weighing 25-2500 grams.	Strength
Blending of product	Using more than one type of tobacco in one product.	Only use one type of tobacco in one product	Only use one type of tobacco in one product	Strength
Price	Prices start from IDR 9,000 - IDR 20,000 for sliced tobacco products	Prices start from IDR 17,000 - IDR 150,000	Prices start from IDR 15,000 - IDR 310,000	Strength

Advertisement	Canvas, Storefront jars, social media (passive), t-shirts, banners, Web (passive)	Web, canvas, social media	Web, canvas, social media	Weakness
Place and distribution	Does not have e-commerce Factory Location: Jl. Kumpul Bambang Suprpto No. 2A, Baciro, Kec. Gondokusuman, City of Yogyakarta, Special Region of Yogyakarta 55225	Have e-commerce (Tokopedia) Factory Location: Puri Cempaka Putih 2 Block AS 29, Bumiayu, Kec. Kedungkandang Malang City, East Java 65135	Does not have e-commerce Factory Location: Jl. Lt. Gen. S. Parman No. 92, Purwantoro, Kec. Blimbing, City of Malang, East Java 65122	Weakness

E. Marketing Mix Analysis

The author uses the 4P marketing mix, because Taru Martani is not a company that provides services. Products are something that can be sold by a company, whether in the form of services, goods, or digital products. PT Taru Martani has two types of products, namely cigars and sliced tobacco. Both are the main products of PT Taru Martani. However, in this study, the authors focused on sliced tobacco products. PT Taru Martani's sliced tobacco products are Violin, Virgin Royal, Royal Bourbon, 18 Rolling Tobacco, Mundi Victor, and Countryman.

Price is the cost that must be incurred by target consumers to buy or use the product offered. Pricing depends on the value of the product that can be felt by consumers. PT Taru Martani's product prices range from low to high, depending on product variations.

Promotion is a way to promote your product in order to reach the target market thereby generating sales. Promotions carried out by PT Taru Martani are currently in the form of canvases, social media content, storefronts, banners, t-shirts. Besides that, Cafe Taru Martani also often provides bundling packages by buying coffee milk which will get a discount. Apart from milk coffee, Taru Martani Cafe has also provided several promos with tobacco rolling bundling packages.

Place refers to the location where consumers can find, use, access or purchase the products provided. Apart from being in the form of a physical location such as a shop, office, factory or warehouse, nowadays elements of a place can also take a digital form such as social media, marketplaces, websites and others. The place owned by PT Taru Martani is a factory located on Jl. Kumpul Bambang Suprpto No. 2A, Baciro, Kec. Gondokusuman, City of Yogyakarta, Special Region of Yogyakarta. Taru Martani products are sold at the Taru Martani Cafe which is in the factory yard. Apart from that, Taru Martani is also sold to several distributors outside the city of Jogja. However, not all tobacco distributors outside the Yogyakarta area sell Taru Martani products, so only certain cities.

F. VRIO Analysis

The VRIO analysis was carried out based on interviews with the Head of the Marketing Division, Taru Martani, and competitor analysis. Following are the results of the VRIO analysis:

	Value	Rarity	Inimitability	Organized	Competitive Advantage
Strength 1: Has a variety of products	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustained competitive advantage
Strength 2: Using more than one type of tobacco in a product to create a distinctive taste	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustained competitive advantage
Strength 3: The company is historical and is under the auspices of the Yogyakarta Palace so that it can have a good reputation and trust regarding the production of sliced tobacco.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustained competitive advantage
Strength 4: Has a low price	Yes	Yes	No		Temporary competitive advantage
Strength 5: Have definite suppliers	No				

G. STP Analysis

Segmentation is classified based on demographics and behavior. Demographics include income/month and age. While the behavior is lifestyle.

Segmenting	1	2	3	4
Demographic				
Income/month	Less than 2 million rupiah	2 million to 3 million rupiah	more than 3 million rupiah	2 million to 3 million rupiah
Age	18-25	26-35	36-45	18-25
Behavior				
Lifestyle	People who like the tradition of rolling tobacco cigarette addict	People who like the tradition of rolling tobacco Cigarette addict	People who like the tradition of rolling tobacco consuming cigar Cigarette addict	People who like the tradition of rolling tobacco Cigarette addict
	Active smoker	people who like hang out (ex: in coffee shop) active smoker	Socialite people Active smoker	People who like hang out Active smoker
	Social media user	Social media user		Social media user

The current company segmentation is shown in the table above, and as can be seen, it is divided into four parts. Various factors that affect segmentation include monthly income, age, location, social class, routines, and lifestyles. Based on the table above, the target market for Taru Martani is segment 2.

The positioning of Taru Martani products is still at the regional level. The majority who know Taru Martani products are people who are in Yogyakarta. In addition, the Saus Iris tobacco product has a target market for smokers who have middle to lower incomes because the price is affordable and relatively cheaper compared to conventional cigarettes that are generally circulating with the same taste. But when compared to electric cigarettes, electric cigarettes are more practical to use.

9 points of marketing positioning:

Target Segment: Target segment 2

Customer Problem: Cigarette prices are increasing due to increased excise duty on certain excise codes, tired of the many cigarettes circulating in the market.

Customer Jobs-To-Be-Done: Fulfilling consumer desires in smoking, preserving traditions and getting the essence of rolling tobacco and consuming cigars, tasting conventional cigarettes.

Frame of Reference: Obtaining a different essence of smoking by rolling the tobacco first (Queen Bee and PT Indonesia Tobacco Tbk).

Basic Requirements: Have sliced tobacco products

Unique Value Proposition: Taru Martani products have their own unique blending, Taru Martani. Taru Martani uses more than 1 type of tobacco in the manufacturing process so that without using any flavor, Taru Martani's products have a unique, distinctive taste. In addition, the various treatments in the tobacco drying process result in a large variety of products.

Reason to Believe: The third oldest cigarette factory in Indonesia. PT Taru Martani, which has been established since 1918, places its brand as a heritage because it is the 3rd oldest tobacco company in Indonesia, its products have been around for a long time. Based on a preliminary survey conducted on 10 consumers, Taru Martani products have a delicious taste and aroma. The product is a blend of several types of tobacco.

Distinction to Competitor: Prices are low compared to competitors.

Emotional Benefit: stress relief, improved mood, social connections, rituals or habits.

Positioning Statement: Taru Martani products are aimed at active smokers who provide the essence of cigarettes in a conventional way. Sliced tobacco products can be aimed at people who want to experience smoking at a lower cost.

H. SWOT Analysis

The TOWS Matrix can assist companies in identifying and developing strategies that are appropriate to the internal and external situations they face.

	Strength (S)	Weakness (W)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Have a variety of products (Marketing Mix) (2) Has a low price (Marketing Mix) (3) A company that has a long history (VRIO). (4) Using more than one type of tobacco in one product variation so that it has a distinctive taste (VRIO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Less active promotional activities (Marketing Mix) (2) Sales promotion only available at Taru Martani Cafe (Marketing Mix) (3) No official online distribution from the company (Marketing Mix) (4) Website is not updated regarding product information (Marketing Mix) (5) Distribution that has not spread in the Yogyakarta area or outside the Yogyakarta area (Marketing Mix) (6) Low brand awareness (Marketing Mix)
Opportunity (O)	S - O Strategy	W - O Strategy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) The decline in the economic conditions of individuals who consume cigarettes will make them switch to cheaper types of cigarettes (PESTLE). (2) Rising exchange rates can also have an impact on industry profitability, because some of Taru Martani's products are exported to other countries (PESTLE). (3) The habits and views of the Indonesian people towards tobacco (PESTLE) (4) The tobacco industry in Indonesia often targets young adults, and social influences (PESTLE). (5) In Indonesia, smoking is often considered as part of the culture and lifestyle (PESTLE). (6) The potential for entrance to industry is low (Porter's 5 Forces) (7) Does not depend on one supplier (Porter's 5 Forces) (8) Product attributes positively influences purchase intention (Customer Analysis) (9) Many product variations (Competitor Analysis) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Advertise Taru sliced tobacco products by communicating product values to consumers, especially focusing on affordable prices and quality excellence (S2, O9, O10) (2) Strengthen brand image with distinctive taste characteristics created in products that use more than one type of tobacco (S4, O3, O8, O9, O11) (3) Use a product diversification strategy. Product diversification at Taru Martani can be seen based on product prices, product variations, and product composition. (S1, S2, S4, O1, O6, O8, O9, O10, O11) (4) Market expansion strategy by taking advantage of increased exchange rates to increase the profitability of exporting Taru Martani products to other 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Taru Martani needs to improve and expand promotional activities by utilizing social media platforms and online marketing channels to increase brand visibility and awareness (W1, W6, O1, O10) (2) Increasing product information updates. In addition, it also communicates about the advantages possessed by Taru Martani to consumers (W4, O1, O8, O9, O10, O11) (3) Expand distribution network (W3, W6, W5, O1, O4) (4) Increasing brand awareness through cultural and lifestyle bases. (W6, O4, O5)

- (10) Taru Martani has the lowest product price when compared to competitors (Competitor Analysis)
- (11) Taru Martani uses more than one type of tobacco in a product, when compared to its competitors (Competitor Analysis)
- countries. By leveraging its reputation and signature to attract market interest (S3, O2, O8, O11)
- (5) Marketing strategy based on culture and lifestyle (S3, O5, O8)

Threat (T)

- (1) The law on tobacco control (PESTLE).
- (2) New types of cigarettes (e-cigarettes) (PESTLE)
- (3) Minister of Finance Regulation 161/PMK.04/2022 explains that tobacco products are subject to import duties. Thus affecting the selling price of tobacco products to be higher (PESTLE)
- (4) Legal actions related to smoking-related illness or death can result in lawsuits and financial losses for tobacco companies (PESTLE).
- (5) Harvest failing due to unpredictable weather fail (PESTLE)
- (6) Competition in a highly competitive industry (Porter's 5 Forces)
- (7) Customers can influence the price and quality of services provided (Porter's 5 Forces)
- (8) There are new types of cigarettes, for example e-cigarettes and cigarettes without having to roll them first (Porter's 5 Forces)
- (9) Distribution of positively influences Brand Awareness (Customer Analysis)
- (10) Brand Awareness positively influences Purchase Intention (Customer Analysis)
- (11) Social Media positively influences Brand Awareness (Customer Analysis)

S - T Strategy

- (1) Product diversification. So that companies can adjust to changing consumer trends and mitigate the impact of regulations affecting traditional tobacco consumption (S1, S2, T1, T3)
- (2) Product innovation and development, with more advanced technology or development of alternative tobacco products that meet growing market demands (S1, S4, T2, T6)
- (3) Focus on product and service quality (S2, S5, T6, T7, T9, T11)
- (4) Strengthen and Communicate product excellence (S3, T2, T6, T10)

W - T Strategy

- (1) Discount Offering and Promotion Strategies. (W1, W2, W3, T1, T10)
- (2) Regional Distribution Expansion Strategy (W3, W5, W6, T1, T3, T9)
- (3) Increase consumer engagement through websites or social media. (W4, W6, T6, T9, T11)

I. QSPM Analysis

QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) is a matrix used to determine strategic priorities to be implemented. Before designing the QSPM matrix, the writer must weight each internal and external factor, which will then be multiplied by the attractive score to get the total attractive score. Weighting uses EFE (External Factor Evaluation) and IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation).

External Factors		Weight
No.	Opportunities	
1	The decline in the economic condition of individuals who consume cigarettes will make them switch to cheaper types of cigarettes, for example sliced tobacco sauce	0.119
2	The tobacco industry in Indonesia often targets young adults, who are particularly vulnerable to peer pressure and social influence, thereby increasing the demand for cigarettes	0.095
3	In Indonesia, smoking is often seen as part of the culture and lifestyle	0.095
4	Product attributes positively influence purchase intention	0.119

No.	Threat	
1	The Indonesian government has passed a law on tobacco control that prohibits tobacco advertising and the sale of tobacco products to children and imposes health warning labels on cigarettes	0.095
2	Technological advances have led to the development of e-cigarettes and other alternative tobacco products, which could impact consumption of traditional tobacco including sliced tobacco sauce	0.095
3	Competition in the industry is very competitive	0.095
4	Distribution affects brand awareness positively	0.095
5	Brand awareness influences purchase intention positively	0.095
6	Social media influences brand awareness positively	0.095
Total		1

Internal Factors		Weight
No.	Strength	
1	The decline in the economic condition of individuals who consume cigarettes will make them switch to cheaper types of cigarettes, for example sliced tobacco sauce	0.156
2	The tobacco industry in Indonesia often targets young adults, who are particularly vulnerable to peer pressure and social influence, thereby increasing the demand for cigarettes	0.125
3	In Indonesia, smoking is often seen as part of the culture and lifestyle	0.156
4	Product attributes positively influence purchase intention	0.156
No.	Weakness	
1	The Indonesian government has passed a law on tobacco control that prohibits tobacco advertising and the sale of tobacco products to children and imposes health warning labels on cigarettes	0.156
2	Technological advances have led to the development of e-cigarettes and other alternative tobacco products, which could impact consumption of traditional tobacco including sliced tobacco sauce	0.125
3	Competition in the industry is very competitive	0.125
Total		1

No.	Strategy Description	QSPM Score
1	Marketing strategy based on culture and lifestyle	5.761
2	Improve and expand promotional activities by leveraging social media platforms and online marketing channels to increase visibility and brand awareness	8.804
3	Increasing product information updates and communicating about the superiority of Taru Martani's products to consumers	8.845
4	Expand distribution network	11.075
5	Focus on product and service quality	4.649
6	Discount and promotion offer strategy	2.647

BUSINESS SOLUTION

There are sixteen strategies resulting from TOWS analysis that can be implemented by Taru Martani to increase brand awareness. However, researchers adjust the strategies that can be implemented by Taru Martani according to Taru Martani's capabilities. Of the sixteen strategies selected, there are six strategies that can be implemented by Taru Martani in the near future. Then from the results of the QSPM analysis, the six strategies have been sorted, which are the first to sixth priority strategies. So based on the results of the author's analysis, the following is the sequence of strategies for Taru Martani:

Expand distribution network

Taru Martani can cooperate with tobacco distributors or agents to expand distribution to areas that have not been covered by Taru Martani. Therefore, Taru Martani must make it easier for customers to find and identify their products if they want to seize the cheap cigarette market, including sliced tobacco.

Increasing product information updates and communicating about the superiority of Taru Martani's products to consumers

The lack of updates regarding product information on Taru Martani's website and social media can be overcome by increasing the number of posts and updating the latest information about products. This can make it easier for consumers and accelerate consumers in purchasing decisions. Taru Martani must convey product values and product advantages clearly, so that these values can be enjoyed by consumers. In addition, being active on social media and increasing interaction with followers can make it easier for companies to analyze consumer desires. This can be in the form of creating interesting content, posting regularly on social media, interacting with followers (replying to comments, direct messages, holding quizzes, etc.), and regularly updating information about product changes.

Improved and expand promotional activities by leveraging social media platforms and online marketing channels to increase visibility and brand awareness

Hold special promotions, discounts or special offers by making product bundling packages with several types of products, bundling packages with tobacco rolling tools, or giving free products for purchases with a specified minimum amount. Utilizing social media to increase social media engagement (increase followers) by holding a giveaway with terms and conditions. This can make people more familiar with products of Taru Martani .

Marketing strategy based on culture and lifestyle

Utilizing the views and habits of the Indonesian people towards tobacco as part of their culture and lifestyle. Taru Martani can communicate traditional values and the authenticity of its products to build emotional relationships with consumers who value these values. This can also strengthen the company's branding and image as a cigarette brand that has a long history and guaranteed quality. This can be done by posting on social media about the culture of smoking sliced tobacco from their ancestors, web design that educates about the history of sliced tobacco and smoking culture, and designing packaging that is unique and attractive by showing cultural values.

Focus on product and service quality

Facing intense competition in the industry and the influence of customers in choosing tobacco products, Taru Martani needs to take advantage of product advantages, maintain the taste of products that have high demand from consumers, improve product quality for products that are less desirable, especially tobacco flavors, and improve service by improving interactions with customers.

Discount and promotion offer strategy

To broaden the consumer base and boost sales, discounts and promotions are made accessible through official online channels, such as websites or applications, in addition to Café Taru Martani. Use efficient web marketing techniques to draw in and keep consumers, such as customer loyalty programs, discounts, or product mashups.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Analysis of external factors used by the author is PESTLE analysis, Porter's Five Forces analysis, customer analysis, and competitor analysis. While the internal factor analysis used by the author is Marketing Mix analysis, VRIO analysis, and STP analysis. From the results of the analysis of these factors obtained external and internal factors that affect business at Taru Martani.

External factors that become opportunities for Taru Martani are decline in economic conditions, social influence to someone, smoking culture and lifestyle, and product attributes, have a lot of suppliers. Meanwhile, external factors that pose a threat to Taru Martani are government regulations on tobacco product control, technology advances, regulations of the Ministry of Finance regarding tobacco customs regulation, crop failures, and e-cigarettes.

The internal factors that have become Taru Martani's strengths are product variations, product prices, company history, and the composition of sliced tobacco that gives it a distinctive taste. While the internal factors that are Taru Martani's weaknesses are low brand awareness, promotion, distribution, and less active websites.

To increase brand awareness and purchase intention the authors suggest expanding the distribution network. Establish partners with distributors in areas that have not been reached by Taru Martani. Making it easier for consumers to obtain and see or get to know Taru Martani products. If the product is widely spread, it can make it easier to replace other brands that run out in a store or area. That way it can increase purchase intention.

B. Recommendation

To increase brand awareness, Taru Martani should expand its distribution network, regularly update product information and create interesting, informative and useful content on social media. In addition, to increase purchase intention, Taru Martani should focus on product attributes and create product campaigns about culture and lifestyle, especially on social media (because it's easier to catch by the audience) to increase brand awareness through culture and lifestyle.

REFERENCES

1. Aaker, D. A. & Kaller, K. L. 1990. *Consumer Evaluation of Brand Extension*. Journal of Marketing. 54(1). pp:c27-41
2. Aditi, Bunga & Hermansyur, H M. 2018. *Pengaruh Atribut Produk, Kualitas Produk dan Promosi, Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Mobil Merek Honda Di Kota Medan*. Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen dan Bisnis, Universitas Harapan: Vol. 19, No. 1.
3. Ahmad, Naveed & Guerrero, Eduardo. 2020. *Influence of Social Media on Brand Awareness: A Study on Small Businesses*. Master Programme in Business Administration (MBA): Business Management. University of Gavle.
4. Akpoyomare, O. B., Patrick, L. P. K. & Ganiyu R. A. 2012. *The Influence of Product Attributes on Consumer Purchase Decision in the Nigerian Food and Beverages Industry : A Study of Lagos Metropolis*. American Journal of Business and Management, 1(4), 196–201.
5. Badan Pusat Statistika. *Ekonomi Indonesia Tahun 2020-2022*. Data is obtained on the website: <http://www.bps.go.id>.
6. Chattopadhyay, T., S. Shivani dan M. Krishnan. 2009. *Marketing Mix Elements Influencing Brand Equity and Brand Choice*. Vikalpa. Vol 35, No 3: 67-84.
7. Gustian. 2013. *Pengaruh Distribution Intensity, Advertising, dan Sales Promotion Terhadap Brand Awareness, dan Brand Equity Pada Produk Sunlight di Surabaya*. Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa manajemen (JUMMA): Universitas Katolik Widya Mandala Surabaya, Vol. 2, No. 3.
8. Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. 2018. *Principle of Marketing (17th ed.)*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
9. Kotler, P.T. and Keller, K.L. 2016. *Marketing Management*. 15th edition, Global Edition. UK: Pearson Education, Inc.
10. Ramos, Angel F., Francisco J. Rondán., & Manuel J. Sánchez-Franco. 2015. *Direct and Indirect Effects of Marketing Effort on Brand Awareness and Brand Image*. University of Seville.
11. Saputro, M. G. 2015. *Analisis Pengaruh Brand Awareness Brand Association, Pucived Quality dan Brand Loyalty Terhadap Purchase Intention Laptop Acer Diponogoro*. Skripsi. Yogyakarta.: Universitas Yogyakarta.
12. Subagio, R.A., Suharyono., & Kusumawati, A. 2015. *Pengaruh Atribut Produk Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Studi pada Konsumen Produk Low Cost Green Car Astra Daihatsu Ayla di PT. Jolo Abadi, Malang)*. Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB), 23(1), 1-9.
13. Tritama, Hansel Bagus & Tarigan, Riswan Efendi. *The Effect of Social Media to The Brand Awareness of A Product of A Company*. CommIT Journal: 10 (1).
14. William, C., dan Japarianto, E. 2016. *Analisis Pengaruh Ekuitas Merek terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Ice Cream De Boliva Surabaya*. Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen. 2(1), pp:13-19.

Cite this Article: Mega Anjani, Prawira Fajarindra Belgiawan (2023). Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness and Purchase Intention of Sliced Tobacco for PT. Taru Martani 1918. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(7), 5021-5032